

COMMUNITY STRUCTURES AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KANO STATE

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Abstract: The study is intended to identify community structures and their areas of involvement in managing senior secondary schools for productive teaching-learning in Kano State, Nigeria. The study specifically intended to achieve the following research objectives: to identify community structures involved with the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State; to identify the areas of participation of the identified community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State. The population of the study comprised the teaching staff, non-teaching staff, officials of Parent- Teachers Association (PTA) and officials of School- Based Management Committee (SBMC) in public secondary schools in Kano State, Nigeria. The officials of the SBMC and PTA included: Chairman/ Chairperson, Vice Chairman, Secretary, Public Relations Officer (PRO) and Treasurer. The population of the study specifically is 20,106. This number 20,106 was obtained from the existing 945 public secondary schools in Kano State as provided by Kano State Secondary Schools Management Board (KSSMB, 2018). The sample size for the study was determined using Research Advisors (2006) Sample Size Table, where 378 respondents were selected. The survey design was used and the instruments for data collection were a questionnaire and an interview schedule. The findings of the study indicated among others that the community structures involved with the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State are: old students association, community development association, women organisation, religious groups, youth's clubs or association, Parent Teachers Association (PTA), School Based Management Committee (SBMC), Community Promotion Committee and Students association. The areas of community structures participation in the management of public secondary schools in Kano State include: planning for the development of the senior secondary schools, teachers training and professional development support, decision making, monitoring and evaluation. It is therefore, recommended among other things that: awareness campaign should be done by government and other stakeholders like community leaders on the importance of creating community structures in the management of public secondary schools. This could be done by the use of mass media and community leaders.

Keywords: community structures, involvement areas, management, senior secondary schools, teaching-learning

Introduction

Education is a powerful catalysing agent and it plays a pivotal role in the development of individuals as well as society. Education ranks at the near top in the social priorities of all countries. Education is a social process and

it receives its meaning and essential logic from the society of which it is a part. In modern societies, education is considered as an indispensable requirement of development and a fundamental right of every individual. This is one of the reasons education is part of the key issues in Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Though MDGs have been reverted into Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), education still maintains its position as one of the components of the SDGs.

Article 7 of the World Declaration on Education for All (W-EFA) adopted in the World Conference on Education for All (WC – A), held in Jomtien Thailand in 1990 called for strengthening partnerships between government and communities in the provision of education for all. The same message was echoed six years later during the 1996 mid – decade implementation review in Amman, Jordan. The final report of that meeting observed that as governments seek ways to decentralise responsibility for education, equalise educational opportunities, and raise more funds, they need strong and innovative allies (Bray, 1996). Therefore, need for the involvement of the community in the management of educational institutions worldwide was identified and realised in the meeting.

The general notion of school management among teachers in secondary schools was entirely based on one individual, the principal - who planned everything for the school. Several workshops organized by the All Nigeria Confederation of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPPS) clearly states that the management of school should not rely on one individual but should be a collective effort of the School Management Team (Nwangwa, 2013). One individual cannot single-handedly take care of the task of school management effectively and efficiently because nobody has the monopoly of knowledge. Therefore, school management should be a collective effort based on the principles of division of labour and decentralisation of power that will yield in better input and output in the education system of the country.

The School Management Team therefore represents the school's management structure which is responsible for implementing the education policies of the country in their schools. The new education system in Nigeriarequires principals of schools to establish the school management teams that will assist in the management of the schools. Therefore, for a better school management, there should be room for the community to participate in the management of the school. For better participation of the community, community structures need to be involved. Community structures are groups, organisations or bodies based in the community and involved with progress and development of the community. They include, among others, women organisation, youths clubs, religious groups and students association. The structures will be of paramount importance in better management of the schools when it comes to division of labour.

It is obvious that government alone cannot single-handedly provide education for all for some reasons among which are: declining budgetary allocation, increase in enrolment and shortfalls in funds due to current global financial crisis which has impacted on the world economy and resulted in lack of materials to implement the various educational programmes effectively and efficiently. In view of this circumstance, the government therefore needs to partner with the other stakeholders, particularly the community through community structures, to supplement the efforts in effective and efficient educational services delivery and management.

Statement of the Problem

There have been myriads of managerial and administrative problems confronting the educational system in Nigeria. Some of these problems are: overcrowded classrooms, dearth of teachers, inadequate infrastructure and

poor funding. The system has not only witnessed decayed facilities and infrastructures, poor funding, poor quality products, low morale of teachers, incessant crisis, and inadequate research but also that the government of Nigeria have been saddled with too many responsibilities; it does not seem to be able or willing to provide solution for solving these problems. These problems have become a recurring demand in the history of Nigerian education.

To salvage the situation, several reforms and strategies were made and adopted, and one of such strategies was involvement of the community structures to participate in the management of public educational institutions, public senior secondary schools included. Community structures participation in the management of public secondary schools helps in addressing managerial and administrative problems. This is in form of supplementing the efforts of government from the other quarters. This is in like adequate physical infrastructural development like building of classrooms, provision of adequate teachers, monitoring teacher teaching activities, school security and student learning support like extra-lesson.

However, the researchers observed that, in practical terms, efforts towards strengthening community participation in school management had emphasised mainly the basic education level. This is particularly in Kano State where State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) Mobilisation Department have been active in community engagement but the Kano State Senior Secondary Schools Management Board (KSSSSMB) that regulates public senior secondary schools had no special initiative targeted at community engagement, yet policy reform requires that communities are to be involved. This is same to Civil Society Organisation (CSO), donor and research initiatives. It becomes important to understand the situation of community structures participation in public senior secondary schools. It is, therefore, in view of this that the study looked into community structures and their areas of involvement in managing public senior secondary schools for productive teaching-learning in Kano state, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The study intended to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify community structures involved with the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State.
2. To identify the areas of participation of the identified community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State.

Research Questions

The research was guided by the following questions with a view to finding appropriate answers to them, the questions are:

1. What are the community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State?
2. What are the areas of community structures participation in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State?

Significance of the Study

This study could help in policy formulation in the management of educational institutions. This is in the sense that from the findings of the study a clear picture of the strategies to be employed in educational managerial policy framework design shall be seen. This could lead to an effective educational services delivery in Kano State. The study could benefit officers in public senior secondary schools and other extra-ministerial parastatals of education in equipping them with better ways of giving a helping hand in community participation activities for effective

senior secondary schools educational services delivery in the State. Furthermore, this study could help parents who are usually concerned about their children's education in playing an active role, and in providing assistance in community structures participation activities in improving senior secondary schools educational services delivery. The study could also be helpful in understanding the importance of Community Structures Participation for the development of education in Kano State and Nigeria in general; and in understanding major factors for success or failure. The study could also be of advantage in recommending community structures participation as a strategy for providing education for all as one of the issues in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The study could be of help in serving as an empirical literature for review in academic research particularly in development studies. The study could be helpful to community structures in acquiring additional knowledge and skills in the practice of community participation in the management of educational institution.

Scope of the Study

The study was restricted to community structures and their areas of involvement in managing public senior secondary schools for productive teaching-learning in Kano state, Nigeria. This is specifically in terms of the community structures participation in planning, management, monitoring and evaluation and decision making.

Public senior secondary schools cover technical colleges, vocational centres and adult education centres that provide senior secondary school education in Kano State. The study was then delimited to community participation in public senior secondary schools, in terms of community structures involvement and the areas they involve in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State.

Literature Review

In this segment of the paper empirical literature relevant to the study is reviewed as follow:

Usaini (2014) also conducted a study on Appraisal of School Improvement through Community Support Initiative: A Case of School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, Kano State. The study appraised the impact of community support initiative in improving school management, with a particular reference to SchoolBased management Committees (SBMC) in Dawakin Kudu Zone, Kano State.

The objectives of the study were to; identify the activities of (SBMC) in selected schools within Dawakin Kudu Local Government Area, Kano State; to assess the scope of the community involvement in the activities of the SBMC, and to determine challenges facing school improvement initiative of the SBMC. The study adopts survey research design. The sample used for the study is two hundred and seventy six (276) school principals/teachers i.e. fifteen (15) principals and two hundred and sixty one (261) teachers and one hundred and sixty (160) members of the SBMC across the 15 selected secondary schools in the study area, which comprises Kumbotso, Warawa and Dawakin Kudu Local Governments. Two sets of instruments were used; the first set is the School Improvement through Community Support Questionnaire (SITCSQ) and the second one is School improvement through Community Support Interview Schedule (SITCSIS).

The findings of the study, which is the resultant output of the generated and processed data include the discovery that activities of the SBMC in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone comprises of active involvement in school budget implementation and maintaining school discipline, administrative functions, students and staff welfare and the repairs and provision of toilet facilities. Similarly, there is high level of community involvement in SBMC

activities especially in the study area. It also found SBMC to be highly effective in improving students' enrolment, school attendance and performance.

The study recommends among other measures that sound and concrete measure should be taken to improve, enhance and encourage community participation in schools activities by the government through the various education parastatals and sensitisation of the public. Finally the research recommends that school administration and management should be decentralized to allow for more committees that would internalize other interest groups and paves way for more advisory bodies to be constituted as part of the school administration. This study conducted by Usaini (2014) highlights the effective role that community participation can play in the development and progress of education and promotion of democracy by decentralisation of the powers for managing educational institutions. The study found that the community, through the platform of SBMC participates in the areas of school budget implementation and maintaining school discipline. These are some of the areas of community structures participation (CSP) in the management of public senior secondary schools. The findings of this study is an addition to these findings, as it found some more other areas of CSP in the management of public senior secondary schools, like planning and decision making.

The findings of this study in the areas aspect is then an extension of what Usaini (2014) discovered. The study by Usaini (2014) is related to this study because it is an appraisal of school improvement through community support initiative. But the study differs with this study in scope and context. This is because the study was conducted within the context of only SBMCs in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, Kano State. But this study covers the whole of community structures and the whole Kano State. This study therefore is wider in scope and context than Usaini (2014) study.

Ugwuanyi (2013) carried out a study on community participation in the administration of secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent of community participation in secondary school administration in the zone. Survey design was adopted for the study. Five research questions and null hypotheses were formulated and used to guide the study. The population of the study comprised all the sixty-two (62) principals and two thousand and four (2004) secondary school teachers in Nsukka Education Zone. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select sixty-two (62) principals and four hundred and sixty-six (466) teachers. The research developed a 43 – items questionnaire titled “Community Participation in the Administration of Secondary School in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State (CPASSQ)” which was used to elicit responses from the respondents. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while T-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings from the data analysis showed that several roles which the communities were expected to play in secondary schools' administration were done at minimal level and not done adequately. There is need for the communities to be actively involved in funding, decision making, infrastructural facilities provision, control of acts of indiscipline and security of the schools. This study was limited to an education zone in the state. The study also focused on principals and teachers alone while the community representatives were left out in the study. In view of these limitations, the present study attempted to fill the gaps by gathering data from the community members as well.

This study by Ugwuanyi (2013) agrees with this study in terms of considering teachers as part of the community, they therefore should be considered as part of research population on community structures participation in the management of public senior secondary schools. However, this study, in addition to teachers added SBMC, PTA officials and non-teaching as part of the research population. This therefore makes this study different to Ugwuanyi (2013) study. By implication this covers a gap in the literature that the study did not cover.

Another study conducted on community participation in educational management is by Onsomu, Mungai, Oulai, Sankale, Mujidi (2004) on Community Schools in Kenya: Case study on Community Participation in Funding and Managing Schools. The study is one of a series of studies that are being carried out at the IIEP and which focus on the issues of financing and managing community schools as well as on the contribution of these schools to the goals of basic education for all in developing countries. Although the term “community schools” may have different meanings in different country contexts, in this study, community schools are defined as schools which are built, financed and managed by the communities themselves, with or without government assistance.

The study made the following findings: despite the long history of community contribution to education in the country, as documented by numerous studies on the Harambee Schools, the recent trend in the development of community schools in Kenya presents different and original features; these new community schools take their roots in economically deprived settlements of suburban Nairobi areas and they have been mushrooming since the late 1980s as the result of a cost-sharing policy that was introduced in education in 1989.

The schools enrolled about 40,837 learners in 2002, representing almost 17 per cent of total enrolment in primary schools in greater Nairobi urban areas. The study also revealed that these schools are constantly expanding their contribution to the achievement of the goal of basic education for all in the country, despite the many challenges facing them. The schools made Dropout rates low and many students remain in schools until Standard 8, the last year in primary education. Some of these schools offer lunch to students, which help to keep them in school.

The 6 Community schools in Kenya Case study on community participation in funding and managing schools mentioned that majority of teachers are poorly paid but they remain in the job because of their commitment to the learners and their parents. The teachers need better supervision from the government and opportunities to upgrade their levels of competency. Infrastructural facilities need to be improved and land ownership is a potential source of conflict between the schools and the churches which very often own the land where schools are built. Although HIV/AIDS was not reported as a serious problem, the presence in these schools of many orphans and children living with a single parent, or with distant relatives, may be interpreted as indications that the pandemic is to some degree affecting the community schools.

The study pointed out the needs for the Ministry of Education to assist these schools to cope with their main problems in the areas of teachers’ salaries, pedagogical improvement, and supervisory services.

From this study, it is evident that community structures participation can adequately help in supplementing the effort of government in educational services delivery and providing education for all. This is because in the study it is discovered that the community schools in Kenya have been able to reduce the number of schools drop outs and maintained pupils in the schools up to the last class in primary education. The teachers in the schools, though poorly paid, but accepted to remain teaching in the schools because of their good rapport with the community.

The study is similar to this study in the sense that it studied community participation in school management. The study differs with this study in aspect of coverage, where this study covered the whole of senior secondary schools in Kano State and the study only covered community schools.

Methodology

Survey design was used and the instruments for data collection were a questionnaire and an interview schedule. The population of the study comprised the teaching staff, non-teaching staff, officials of Parent- Teachers Association (PTA) and officials of School- Based Management Committee (SBMC) in public secondary schools in Kano State, Nigeria. The officials of the SBMC and PTA included: Chairman/ Chairperson, Vice Chairman, Secretary, Public Relations Officer (PRO) and Treasurer. The population of the study specifically is 20,106. This number 20,106 was obtained from the existing 945 public secondary schools in Kano State as provided by Kano State Secondary Schools Management Board (KSSMB, 2018).The sample size for the study was determined using Research Advisors (2006) Sample Size Table, where 378 respondents were selected. The data analysis tools used were frequency count, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation.

Data Analysis, Results, Findings and Discussion

The chapter presents analysis of the data, results, discussion and findings in the research, that provide answers to the research questions. **Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents**

S/N	Sample category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Sex:		
	Male	321	84.9%
	Female	57	15.1%
	Total	378	100%
2	Age:		
	51 – above	43	11.4%
	42 – 49	80	21.2%
	34 – 41	165	43.7%
	26 – 33	68	18.0%
	18 – 25	22	5.8%
	Total	378	100%
3	Occupation:		
	Trading	139	36.8%
	Civil Servant	151	40.0%

Handcraft	73	19.3%
Others	15	04.0%
Total	378	100%
<i>Klover Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation</i>		
Volume 3, Issue 1, January - March 2025	75	19.8%
ISSN: 2995-4215	96	25.4%
Impact Factor: 7.94	179	47.4%
https://kloverjournals.org/index.php/mri		
Others	28	7.4%
Total	378	100%
5 Category:		
Teaching Staff	113	29.9%
Non-teaching Staff	38	10.0%
PTA Official	76	20.1%
SBMC Official	151	40.0%

Source: Research Survey (2019)

Male respondents constituted 84.9% (321) and 15.1% (57) were female as data indicated above in the table. This indicates that more male members of the community were involved in community participation in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State; this may be due to cultural beliefs. Subsequently, 51 – above years of age constituted 11.4% (43), 42 – 49 constituted 21.2% (80), 34 – 41 years constituted 43.7% (165), 26 - 33 constituted 18.0% (68) and 18 – 25 constituted 5.8% (22) of the sample. The percentage (%) of respondents of 51 and above years of age and that of those of 18-25 years of age were the smallest of the age percentages of the respondents; where 51 and above had 11.4% and 18-25 had 5.8%. This is an indicator of that the respondents were more matured youths, not older youths of 51 years of age and above and not fresher youths of the age of 18-25 years of age. This as well determines that the community members who participate in the management of the public senior secondary schools in Kano State were matured youths with a combination of youth agility and mental maturity. This would translate into proper disposition and better yields in the management of the public senior secondary schools.

In terms of occupation, 36.8% (139) constituted trading, while 40% (151) constituted civil servant, 19.3% (73) constituted handcraft and 15% (4) constituted others from the sample. This indicates that the respondents were more engaged with an economic activity that will give them the ability to contribute materially by, for example, making financial contributions in managing the public senior secondary schools. This is because they all had a means of making a living that will make them more responsible. The level of education of the respondents in the data constituted that 19.8% (75) had primary education, 25.4% (96) had secondary education, 47.4% (179) had tertiary education and 7.4% (28) constituted others. This indicates that majority of the respondents were educated with at least primary school education. The majority of the respondents being educated will surely play role in making them better participants in the management of the public senior secondary schools in the State. This is because education normally makes better people. Additionally, in the case of category, 29.9% (113) of the respondents constituted teaching staff, 10.0% (38) constituted non-teaching staff, 20.1% (76) constituted PTA officials and 40.0% (151) constituted SBMC officials. This indicates that the percentage of the respondents' segment that constituted community members was higher. This was because more community members should be consulted in collecting data for the research and the community members make their presence in PPBEIs management through the platforms of SBMC and PTA. This makes a proper approach in appraising community participation in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State.

Research Question One

What are the community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State? Table 1 contains the data and result:

Table 1 Community Structures in the Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State (N=378)

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Old students association	2.9630	.42930	Agree Committee
2	Community development association	3.1481	.52448	Agree
3	Students association	2.8889	.87605	Agree
4	Women organisation	2.5185	.68785	Agree
5	Religious groups	2.9259	.71721	Agree
6	Youths clubs or associations	2.5556	.95708	Agree
7	Community Promotion Committee	2.9339	.89997	Agree
8	Parents-Teachers Association	2.9894	.90674	Agree
9	School-Based Management	3.1032	.91694	Agree

Source: Research Survey (2019)

The table 1 indicates nine examples of community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State. The community structures included: - old students association with the mean 2.9630 and standard deviation .42930, community development association with the mean 3.1481 and standard deviation .52448, students association with the mean 2.8889 and standard deviation .87605, women organisation with the mean 2.5185 and standard deviation .68785, religious groups with the mean 2.9259 and standard deviation .71721 youths clubs or association with the mean 2.5556 and standard deviation .95708, Community Promotion Committee with the mean 2.9339 and standard deviation .89997, Parents-Teachers Association with the mean 2.9894 and standard deviation .90674 and School-Based Management Committee with the mean 3.1032 and standard deviation .91694.

The analysis of data as presented in Table 1 above showed the mean responses of old students' association, community development association, students association, women organisation, religious groups, youth clubs or association, Community Promotion Committee, Parents-Teachers Association and School-Based Management Committee with their corresponding standard deviations. Data analysis as presented in Table 4.2 revealed that the respondents agreed on all the items (1 to 9). All the items meet the criterion of 2.50 and above at four-point rating scale. This indicates that the community structures that participate in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State are: old students association, community development association, student's association, women organisation, religious groups, youth clubs or association, Community Promotion Committee, Parents-Teachers Association and School-Based Management Committee.

Research Question Two

What are the areas of community structures participation in the management of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State? Table 2 contains the data and result:

Table 2: Areas of Community Structures Participation in the Management of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State (N= 378)

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Planning for the development of the senior secondary schools	2.7037	.76185	Agree
2	Monitoring and evaluation	2.0741	.85861	Disagree
3	Decision making	2.1481	1.00885	Disagree
4	Teachers training and development	2.0000	.98261	Disagree

Source: Research Survey (2019)

Table 2 indicates four variables as the areas of community structures participation in the management of Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State. The areas included:- planning for the development of the senior secondary schools with the mean 2.7037 and standard deviation .76185, monitoring and evaluation with the mean 2.0741 and standard deviation .85861, decision making with the mean 2.1481 and standard deviation 1.00885 and teachers training and development with the mean 2.0000 and standard deviation .98261.

The data analysis as presented in Table 2 above showed the mean responses of planning for the development of the senior secondary schools, monitoring and evaluation, decision making and teachers training and development with their corresponding standard deviations. Data analysis as presented in Table 2 revealed that the respondents agreed on only one item (planning for the development of the senior secondary schools) and disagreed on the other three items (11 to 13). In this case it is only one item that meets the criterion of 2.5 and above at four point rating scale. This indicates that the community structures participate in planning for the development of the senior secondary schools and do not participate in monitoring and evaluation, decision making and teachers training and development.

Summary of Findings

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following were discovered:

1. The community structures involved with the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State are: old students association, community development association, women organisation, religious groups, youth clubs or association, Parent Teachers Association (PTA), School Based Management Committee (SBMC), Community Promotion Committee and Students association.
2. The areas of community structures participation in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State include: planning for the development of the senior secondary schools, teachers training and professional development support, decision making and monitoring and evaluation.

Discussion of the findings

The following are the discussions on each individual result of each of the research questions previously presented, those from the research questionnaire and the research interview combined:-

Research Question One: In the findings the following have been identified as the community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools (PSSSs) in Kano State: old students association, community development association, women organisation, religious groups, youths clubs or association, Parent Teachers Association (PTA), School Based Management Committee (SBMC) comprising representatives of pupils, old students, community leadership, community religious leadership, Community Promotion Committee and Students association like Zawaki Students Association (ZASA). Mean score and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, including this research question one. In this research question, the mean scores of all the items meet the criterion of 2.5 and above at four point rating scale. This shows that the respondents agreed on the items being the community structures that participate in the management of PSSSs in Kano State.

The discovery of these community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State buttresses the point World Bank (1999) made, as reviewed in the literature, that: Every faction of society plays its role in children education, in one way or the other. The presence of these community structures is also in congruence with the point made by Epstein (1995). He says: how to help children succeed in school and later life is by involving partnerships of schools, families and communities who help in improving school programmes and environment, provide family services, increase parents' skills and leadership, liaise with other communities and help teachers with their work. Efforts must be undertaken to join together the efforts for better yields. That can be effectively done if there is effective collaboration between schools, parents and other community groups. Additionally, the finding is also in support of what Heneveld and Craig (1996) recognised of parent and community support as one of the key factors to determine school effectiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa. Sujatha (2000) observed that community participation is in two levels, one is at group level and the other is at individual level. At group level participation representative bodies of the community is large and effective, facilitating the formulation of community-based institutions. This observation shows that community participation is more effective and proper if it is done in groups. This supports the idea of the existence of community structures in Kano State as the ones identified in this study. Therefore, community structures are very important components in the management of educational institutions and particularly the PSSSs. Additionally, community can effectively and properly participate in the management of PSSSs on the platform of community structures.

Research Question Two: Subsequently, in the findings the following have been identified as the areas of community structures participation in the management of public post-basic educational institutions in Kano State: planning for the development of the senior secondary schools, teachers training and development, discipline, skill acquisition, security, decision making, monitoring and evaluation, staff welfare and development, maintenance and repairs. In the mean score of the responses to the questionnaire items on this research question (Research Question Two), the respondents agreed on all the items. Additionally, the findings from the interview responses also indicate that the four areas of the community participation in the questionnaire are the areas of community participation in the management of PSSSs in Kano State. More areas in addition to these, like maintenance and repairs, skill acquisition and security were mentioned by the respondents to the interview.

Therefore, this finding is in agreement with the findings in Usaini (2014) where she says: The findings of my study, which is the resultant output of the generated and processed data include the discovery that activities of the SBMC in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone comprises active involvement in school budget implementation and maintaining school discipline, administrative functions, students and staff welfare and the repairs and provision of toilet facilities.

In another instance, the finding is an extension on what Usaini (2014) discovered as more other areas of community participation in the management of public post-basic educational institutions have been discovered, specifically areas like skill acquisition, security and monitoring and evaluation. This finding also supports the assertion made by Ugwuanyi (2013) that, there is need for the communities to be actively involved in funding, decision making, infrastructural facilities provision, control of acts of indiscipline and security of the schools. This is because school management cannot do without these. This is because decision making, monitoring and evaluation, planning and teacher training and development are the most important components of educational management. They also play a very vital role in achieving the objectives of schools.

Summary and Conclusion

The study looked into community structures and their areas of involvement in managing public senior secondary schools for productive teaching-learning in Kano state, Nigeria. The study started by providing a background of the study that prompted it, a statement of the study problem, objectives of the research or study, questions that the study wanted to find answers to them, significance of the study and scope and delimitation of the study. Additionally, relevant literatures to the study were reviewed.

The study employed survey design because of its appropriateness to the research problem, as the subjects of the study were not controlled. A sample of 378 respondents was used. Two instruments (a researcher made questionnaire and interview schedule) were used to collect data. The data were collected by administering the questionnaire and the interview schedule to the respondents. The data collected were categorized with regards to the research question they answered to serve as the data base of the research. After having the data base of the research on ground, it was analyzed to give some meaning that allowed for it to be understood and interpreted properly. Descriptive statistics i.e simple percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation was used in form of tables. The tables were considered and used, and the results on the research questions and their discussions were made.

In conclusion, the study described, appraised and found community structures and the areas of their involvement as an effective phenomenon in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State. This was because the community structures were found to be viable in the schools management, particularly in the areas they get involved, as explained in this chapter. Therefore, the researcher concludes that community structures are of paramount importance in the management of PSSSs in Kano State.

Recommendations of the Study

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made for improving community structures participation in the management of public senior secondary schools in Kano State:

1. Awareness campaign should be done by government and other stakeholders like community leaders on the importance of creating community structures in the management of public senior secondary schools. This could be done by the use of mass media and community leaders.
2. Community groups should conduct research to identify and participate in other areas of public senior secondary schools management, depending on their capacity, for a comprehensive management and participation in the affairs of the PSSSs and better educational outcomes in Kano State community.

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